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Agricultural Transformation Agenda – Nigeria Mechanization Requirement

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Abstract

The task of transforming agricultural productivity has been a great challenge to various tiers of governments in Nigeria. This paper discussed the various programs embarked upon by previous and present governments all with the aim of boosting agricultural production through tractorization which is an arm of mechanization. The paper reviewed critically the previous attempts and came up with some recommendations to address the tractorization needs of the country. However, there is the need to come up with an agricultural mechanization and tractorization policy for Nigeria which should cover mechanical, draught animal, wind energy, solar power and hydro power that generate power for farm use. This policy should drive the agricultural mechanization policy and also the policy should not be politicized for it to achieve the intended purpose – mechanizing Nigerian agriculture.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The task of achieving self-sufficiency in food production in Nigeria is of high priority to government of Nigeria and revitalizing the nation's economy through the transformation of Nigeria's agriculture to its eminent position is not negotiable. Nigeria has a land area of 93.8 million hectares out of which 40 million hectares are arable land (FAOSTAT, 2014). Presently less than half of this land area is being put into productive use due to various factors that include low level of agricultural mechanization. Majority of Nigerian farmers till this day are still utilizing the traditional methods of farming, which is considered inadequate and inappropriate for the ever increasing population. Global trends in developed and developing countries are increasingly casting dark clouds on peasant and subsistence farming. Presently, Nigeria has engaged about 28.2 million hectares which is dominated largely by subsistence farmers that utilized hoe and cutlass for the farming operations. It is therefore, necessary that the federal government policy embraces agricultural mechanization strategy that would not only remove drudgery from agricultural activities but also create the necessary surpluses for export and create jobs that will reduce the current embarrassing levels of unemployment. The inability of the system to arrest youth restiveness and harness same for agricultural mechanization purposes is one of the causes of insurgency in the country and around the world.

2.0 TECHNOLOGICAL REQUIREMENT IN AGRICULTURE

Technology is any practical process which utilizes scientific knowledge to obtain the desired result with the primary aim of advancing and enhancing human society and conditions. Technology is used to harness the forces of nature and transform the resources that nature has bestowed on man, into goods and services for better quality of life (Oni, 2009).

Traditional technologies are the simplest and most basic technology used in agricultural mechanization in Nigeria and to some extent also applied to commercial agriculture. These technologies range from the traditional cutlasses and hoes, to the developed stick and stone tools used in processing of agricultural produce. These hand tool technologies use man as a power source and are inefficient and ineffective for commercial agriculture. Man is limited to about 0.745 kW continuous power output and is therefore, grossly inefficient as a primary source of power. In most parts of Nigeria where arable farmers are predominantly peasants, traditional technologies are still employed for agricultural production and processing activities.

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The next level of traditional technology is the substitution of human power with animal muscle power. A large variety of implements and machines have been developed which use animals as the principal power source especially for tillage and post-harvest operations. According to Ajav (2000), the current animal traction areas of the country can be classified into four distinct regions, namely:

- Active Animal Traction Region (AATR)
- Semi-Active Animal Traction Region (SAATR)
- Introductory Animal Traction Region (IATR)
- None Animal Traction Region (NATR)

Due to the shortcomings of use of animal traction, the boom of industrialization has found its way into agriculture, lots of processes in agriculture has been revolutionized by means of mechanization, giving rise to agricultural mechanization.

Agricultural Mechanization is defined as a process of development that introduces mechanized assistance of various forms and at any level of technological sophistication in agricultural production in order to reduce human drudgery, improve timeliness and efficiency of various farm operations, bring more land under cultivation, preserve the quality of agricultural products, provide better living conditions and markedly advance the economic growth of the rural sector (NCAM, 1986). This process has not been fully exploited in Nigeria and thus responsible for the drifting away of youths from the profession to other jobs. In developed economies such as that in America, agriculture plays an important role because it has employed mechanization, *termed as modernization*, in virtually all its agricultural processes. Mechanization does not have to be completely home-grown but could also be out-sourced and utilized by engineers, farmers and entrepreneurs for improved agricultural production. This is not to jeopardize the effort of our local fabricators but to put on record that there is no country that has all it takes to mechanize agriculture by herself without importing some machinery or equipment.

It is obvious that Nigeria's agriculture has to be modernized and powered by tractors among other farm power sources if we are to achieve sustainable food security and keep young talented Nigerians in agriculture. Recent estimates indicate that Nigeria has about 40,000 units of tractors out of which only half are functional. Full tractorization of Nigeria's agriculture, according to FAO stipulates tractorization intensity of 1.5hp/ha and a requirement of between 1,500,000 and 2,000,000 units of tractors depending on tractor horse power selection. The 40,000 units include the 30,000 units estimated to have been in the country before 2005 and about 10,000 units procured by the three tiers of government, as well as the private sector between 2005 and 2009. With the potential national cultivable land of 40 million hectares, this number of tractors translates to a tractorization intensity of about 0.04 hp/ha.

Attempts by past administration to make more tractors available to Nigerian farmers have largely been limited by budgetary constraints and lack of adequate facilities and infrastructure. Similarly, inadequate entrepreneurial ability and lack of transparency have caused several tractor hiring services, (especially those run by government) to fold up prematurely (Abba Sayyadi Ruma 2010). Several tractors have been brought into the country and are employed nationwide through several bodies. The ranges of tractors majorly in use within the Nigeria agricultural sector are as tabled below.

Table 1: Tractor power ranges and their availability in Nigeria

Tractor Size	Power Range (kW)	Remarks
Small tractors	Below 26	Not common in Nigeria but very popular in South East Asia.
Medium	50 – 70	Very popular in Nigeria
Large	80 and above	Very few and complicated

Source: Musa, 1996.

3.0 TRACTORIZATION OF NIGERIAN AGRICULTURE

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The first major thrust in tractorization in Nigeria was the establishment of two tractor assembly plants in 1980, namely the National Truck Company (Fiat) in Kano and Steyr Nigeria Ltd in Bauchi, which are no longer in existence. Figure 1 shows the trend of tractors sold by the companies from 1979 to 1983. From the figure, importation and sales of tractors like Massey Ferguson, Ford and John Deere started in 1979 with 600 units, and increased to 2055 units in 1981 and decreased to 660 units in 1983. While indigenously assembled tractors like Steyr and Fiat commenced sales with 900 and 950 units of tractors respectively in 1980; and later sales dropped to 450 and 570 units of tractors respectively in 1982. More so, the capacity utilization was highest (91%) in 1981 for Steyr and lowest (19%) for Fiat in 1982 and 1983 respectively. Each company had sold about 3,000 and 2,000 tractors per year respectively. Each company assembled two tractor models – one in the 60-kW/80-hp range and the other in the 80-kW/110-hp range (Makanjuola, 1984).

Figure 1: The trend of tractors sold in Nigeria.

From the National Investigative Survey Report, it revealed that as at 1985, the total number of four wheel tractors in Nigeria was 5,866. Out of this numbers, 5,288 units were purchased in 1981 alone. This was the period of the Federal Government Green Revolution programme (NCAM, 1986). These tractors were deployed in many areas of tractor applications in agriculture are as follows: -

- i). land development, comprising of both primary and secondary tillage operations;
- ii). planting operations;
- iii). weeding operations through the use of boom sprayers and cultivators;
- iv). harvesting operation using the combine harvester or any other type of tractor mounted/trailed harvester;
- v). post-harvest operations through the use of the tractor power take-off (PTO); and
- vi). dry season farming activities, such as irrigation.

In less recent times, the Cooperative Tractorization Programme through Public Private Partnership (PPP) was introduced in the year 2008 with the sole objective of enhancing and encouraging large scale mechanized farming through tractorization. In a bid to ensure that this was achieved, the Federal Government embarked on the procurement and distribution of tractors and implements to farmers. In two (2) years (2006 and 2007), about 1880 units of tractors were procured by the Federal Government, half of which were sold to farmers and other agriculturally related agencies at 25% subsidy. Recent assessment of the programme was scored low and the impact of this policy was not felt much by the beneficiaries.

However, the government under President Mohammadu Buhari, the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD), Agricultural and Equipment Hiring Enterprise metamorphosed into National Agricultural Mechanization and Equipment Leasing Company (NAMEL) with the primary aim of rendering value added services, such as leasing/hiring out of various kinds of agricultural equipment for land preparation, harvesting and post-harvesting, repairs and maintenance of such equipment and as an incubator

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for training of personnel within farming communities. A farmer can walk into an AEHE center and lease/hire agricultural machines to mechanize farm operations for a fee without necessarily owning such machines. AEHE funding model has been put in place for an effective implementation. AEHE has recorded successes since 2014 when the model of AEHE was established with over 600 units of Tractors and various agricultural equipment, which has been deployed to set up 113 AEHE centers across the nation.

NAMEL is expected to make the equipment available upon receipt of the FMARD 35%. FMARD will at interval remit to NAMEL and Partners the 35% of whatever funding provided in the budget. The amount of 65% counterpart funds to be provided by NAMEL shall be solely dependent on the amount of funding provided by FMARD for each specific implementation phase. NAMEL will be expected to show to the promoters through the M&E report the level of successes of the set-out goals in the key performance indicators (KPI).

NAMEL is expected to operate its own Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) separately while FMARD should also operate its own M&E to serve as check and balances and to enable separate reports analysis monitor the achievement of the collective goals. The vendor partners are expected to bring in the tractors in form of CKD for the purposes of assembling it locally to develop the capacity.

4.0 CONSTRAINTS OF PREVIOUS TRACTORIZATION PROGRAMME

The followings were constraints of the previous tractorization programme: -

- i). Despite the gesture of the Federal Government to facilitate the implementation of the 2008 tractorization programme, the performance of the Private Sector Operators (PSOs) was rated low. As at November, 2009, since the partnership agreements were signed and the PSOs mobilized, only five (5) PSOs out of sixteen (16) selected for the tractorization programme performed.
- ii). The past Tractorization Programmes did not consider critical issues like timeliness, accessibility, affordability and sustainability.
- iii). The States were not carried along in the selection process of arriving at vendors, types and models of tractors and as such did not want to participate in the programme.
- iv). Lack of established Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) between the vendors and the beneficiaries created a lot of disconnect in the implementation of the Tractorization Programmes.

So far, the Federal and State Governments has remained a major buyer of tractors and their associated implements in Nigeria, which has been froth with bureaucratic bottlenecks and very low impact at farmers' level.

5.0 LAND CLEARING AND TRACTOR REQUIREMENTS FOR THE TRANSFORMATION OF NIGERIAN AGRICULTURE

This paper would be incomplete without projecting the requirement for land clearing operations for the projected land area to be utilized for the cultivation of the various identified crops. It must be understood that tractors are not land clearing equipment and as such provision should be made in the tractorization programme for land clearing operations. This is imperative to avoid breakages and ensure that the life span of the tractors are optimized. This paper utilized the projected area to estimate the land clearing equipment that would be required for the cultivation of the land area. In the same vein, the tractor requirements for the cultivation of the projected land area are also estimated. The tractor being referred to in this write-up include plough, harrow, ridger and trailer since tractor is the source of power and not the tillage implement. Summarily below are the submissions for the tractor requirement for the proposed crops.

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Name of agricultural commodity: Rice – Parboiled Brown

Year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
Land Requirement	-	148,148	555,556	555,556	285,714
Land Clearing					
ha/yr cleared by 1 Bull Dozer	540	540	540	540	540
Total Bull Dozer Required	-	274	1,029		
Tractor Requirement with its associated implements					
FAO Tractorization intensity (hp/ha)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Tractor (65 hp)	-	3,419	12,821	12,821	6,593

A

B

Figure A and B are the annual bull dozer and tractor requirements respectively, required to cultivate the projected area of land annually. With a bull dozer clearing average farm land of 540 hectares per year, a total of 274 bull dozers will be required to develop a projected farm land of about 148,148 hectares while a total 1,029 bull dozers will be required to clear a projected farm land of 555,556 ha for year 3. Bull dozers purchased in the first year can be use in subsequent years. This accounts for the null values projected for other years. About 4,444 tractors would be required to prepare a total of 148,148 projected hectares. Tractors may increase as the hectrage (land area) increases. This is to ensure good service delivery and efficiency in tractorization.

Name of Agricultural Commodity: Rice – Parboiled Finished

Year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
Land requirement	-	197,531	555,556	1,620,370	1,375,661
Land Clearing					
ha/yr cleared by 1 Bull Dozer)	540	540	540	540	540
Total Bull Dozer Required	-	366	1,029	3,001	0
Tractor Requirement with its associated implements					
FAO Tractorization intensity (hp/ha)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Tractor (65 hp)	-	4,558	12,821	37,393	31,746

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Annual Bull Dozer Requirement for Parboiled Finished Rice

The same number of Bull Dozers purchased in the first year could be use in subsequent years.

Annual Tractor Requirement (65hp) for Parboiled Finished Rice

The same number of Tractors purchased in the first year could be use in subsequent years .

Name of agricultural commodity: Rice – Milled

Year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
Land requirement (ha)	-	-	44,444	115,226	244,444
Land Clearing					
ha/yr cleared by 1 Bull Dozer)	540	540	540	540	540
Total Bull Dozer Required	-	-	82		
Tractor Requirement with its associated implements					
FAO Tractorization intensity (hp/ha)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
ha/yr Prepared by Power Tiller	5	5	5	5	5
Annual Power Tiller Required	-	-	7,111	18,436	39, 111
Annual Tractor Required (65 hp)	-	-	2	5	11

Annual Bull Dozer Requirement for Milled Rice
The same number of Bull Dozers purchased in the first year could be use in subsequent years.

Y1 Y2 Y3 Y4 Y5

Annual Power Tiller Requirement for Milled Rice
The same number of Power Tiller purchased in the first year could be use in subsequent years. This assumes 80% power tiller utilization.

Y1 Y2 Y3 Y4 Y5

Annual Tractor (65hp) Requirement for Milled Rice
The same number of Tractor purchased in the first year could be use in subsequent years. This assumes 20% tractor utilization.

Y1 Y2 Y3 Y4 Y5

Name of agricultural commodity: Cassava – HFCS

Year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
Land requirement	-	17,051	26,524	32,553	38,195
Land Clearing					
ha/yr cleared by 1 Bull Dozer)	540	540	540	540	540
Total Bull Dozer Required	-	32	49		

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Tractor Requirement with its associated implements	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
FAO Tractorization intensity (hp/ha)	-	512	796	977	1,146
Tractor (70 hp)	-	365	568	698	818

Y1 Y2 Y3 Y4 Y5

Y1 Y2 Y3 Y4 Y5

Name of agricultural commodity: Cassava – Chips for Export

Year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
Land requirement	-	39,787	72,942	119,360	184,610
Land Clearing	540	540	540	540	540
ha/yr cleared by 1 Bull Dozer)	-	74	135		
Total Bull Dozer Required					
Tractor Requirement with its associated implements	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
FAO Tractorization intensity (hp/ha)	-	1,194	2,188	3,581	5,538
Tractor (70 hp)	-	853	1,563	2,558	3,956

Y1 Y2 Y3 Y4 Y5

Y1 Y2 Y3 Y4 Y5

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Name of agricultural commodity: Cassava – Starch

Year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
Land requirement	12963	14286	29630	41414	77333
Land Clearing	540	540	540	540	540
ha/yr cleared by 1 Bull Dozer)	-	74	135		
Total Bull Dozer Required					
Tractor Requirement with its associated implements	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
FAO Tractorization intensity (hp/ha)	-	1,194	2,188	3,581	5,538
Tractor (70 hp)	278	306	635	887	1,657

Annual Bull Dozer Requirement for Cassava Starch
The same number of Bull Dozers purchased in the first year could be use in subsequent years.

Annual Tractor Requirement (70hp)
The same number of Tractor purchased in the first year could be use in subsequent years.

Name of agricultural commodity: Cassava – HQCF

Year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
Land requirement	-	22,857	43,457	48,485	62,578
Land Clearing	540	540	540	540	540
ha/yr cleared by 1 Bull Dozer)					
Total Bull Dozer Required	-	42	80		
Tractor Requirement with its associated implements	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
FAO Tractorization intensity (hp/ha)	-	490	931	1,039	1,341
Tractor (70 hp)					

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Name of agricultural commodity: Sorghum – Malt

Year	1	2	3	4	5
Land requirement	395,062	296,296	460,905	543,210	434,568

Land Clearing

ha/yr cleared by 1 Bull Dozer)	540	540	540	540	540
Total Bull Dozer Required	732	549	854		

Tractor Requirement with its associated implements

FAO Tractorization intensity (hp/ha)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Tractor (60 hp)	9,877	7,407	11,523	13,580	10,864

Name of agricultural commodity: Sorghum – Fortified Food

Year	1	2	3	4	5
Land requirement	-	123,457	164,609	160,494	177,778

Land Clearing

ha/yr cleared by 1 Bull Dozer)	540	540	540	540	540
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Total Bull Dozer Required	-	229	305		
Tractor Requirement with its associated implements					
FAO Tractorization intensity (hp/ha)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Tractor (60 hp)	-	3,086	4,115	4,012	4,444

Y1 Y2 Y3 Y4 Y5

Y1 Y2 Y3 Y4 Y5

Name of agricultural commodity: Cocoa – Beans

Year	1	2	3	4	5
Land requirement	800,000	800,000	800,000	800,000	800,000
Land Clearing					
ha/yr cleared by 1 Bull Dozer)	540	540	540	540	540
Total Bull Dozer Required	1,481	1,481	1,481		
Tractor Requirement with its associated implements					
FAO Tractorization intensity (hp/ha)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Tractor (70 hp)	17,143	17,143	17,143	17,143	17,143

Y1 Y2 Y3 Y4 Y5

Y1 Y2 Y3 Y4 Y5

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Name of agricultural commodity: Cotton					
Year	1	2	3	4	5
Land requirement	148148	222222	333333	296296	388889
Land Clearing					
ha/yr cleared by 1 Bull Dozer)	540	540	540	540	540
Total Bull Dozer Required	274	412	617		
Tractor Requirement with its associated implements					
FAO Tractorization intensity (hp/ha)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Tractor (70 hp)	3,704	5,556	8,333	7,407	9,722

6.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

For tractorization programme to have the desired impact on the agricultural sector of the Nigerian economy, the following recommendations are proposed:-

- i). The private sector (farmers), machinery manufacturers and Agricultural Machinery and Equipment Fabricators Association of Nigeria (AMEFAN) should be invited to a meeting by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development where all the issues that affect stakeholders would be discussed and agreement on the implementation strategy reached. The thrust of the discussion would be on a well packaged marketing strategy that would achieve high implementation performance.
- ii). A meeting of all the stakeholders should be convened at the instance of the Honourable Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development where all the roles and obligations of each stakeholder would be clearly spelt out. The meeting should also include representatives of Cooperative farmer groups from the states. It is expected that at the end of the meeting, all the stakeholders would have full understanding tractorization programme implementation strategy;
- iii). The outputs and sustainability should be properly spelt out so as to realistically measure the performance of the tractorization component of the tractorization programme;
- iv). Tractors and implements acquisition should be limited to four (4) brands for a start. The four (4) brands must be tested and certified by the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM);

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- v). Government should put in place a practicable agricultural mechanization and tractorization policy for Nigeria which should cover mechanical, draught animal, wind energy, solar power and hydro power that generate power for farm use over a defined period;
- vi). Acquisition of tractors and implements through bilateral agreement that would require tractors and implements partners to establish tractors and equipment manufacturing and assembly plants in the country within a specified period should be looked into;
- vii). The manufacturers should be compelled to establish a well-stocked maintenance and servicing workshop to ensure that the tractors and implements are properly maintained and sustained
- viii). Establishment of an effective monitoring and evaluation structure that will ensure proper and cost effective implementation of the tractorization programme; and
- ix). Periodic surveys should be carried out to generate tractors and implements data for planning purposes.

7.0 Conclusion

To successfully mechanize the agricultural sector of the Nigerian economy, it requires that the land clearing and tractorization needs of the agricultural lands should be properly appraised and implemented with the primary aim of making farming attractive to the youths and by extension eliminating unemployment. This paper has taken critical look at the land clearing and tractorization requirement for the projected land area to be utilized for the crop production in the tractorization programme. It is expected that if the land clearing activities is properly addressed through provision of agricultural land clearing services to farmers, many of the populace would delve into agricultural production thus increasing food and fibre for the entire population and provide raw materials for the small, medium and large scale agro industries.

REFERENCES

- i. *Abba Sayyadi Ruma (2010). Private Sector led Community Cooperative Tractor Hiring Service under the Public Private Partnership (PPP) Arrangement. Address delivered at the launching of the Private Sector led Community Cooperative Tractor Hiring Service on Thursday, February 25th, 2010, FCT, Abuja.*
- ii. *Ajav, E. A. (2000). Animal Traction as a Source of Power for Agricultural Development in Nigeria. <http://www.atnesa.org>.*
- iii. *FAOSTAT (2013). A Statistical yearbook of the Food and agricultural organization for the year 2013. In FAO Statistical Yearbook 2013 World food and agriculture.*
- iv. *Makanjuola G. A. (1984). Agricultural Mechanization in Nigeria. In: A. Moens and A. H. J. Siepman (Hrsg.): Development of the Agricultural Machinery Industry in Developing Countries. Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference, Amsterdam, January 23 – 26, 1984. Pudoc Wageningen, 1984, 185 – 193.*
- v. *Musa, H. L. (1996). The Role of Appropriate Mechanization Technology in Agricultural Development in Nigeria. Proceeding of the National Workshop on Appropriate Agricultural Mechanization for Skill Development in Low-Cost Agricultural Mechanization Practices.*
- vi. *NCAM (1986). Agricultural Machinery Inventory, Type and Condition in Nigeria (1975 – 1985). A national survey report prepared by Anazodo, U. G. N., T. O. Abimbola and J. A. Dairo.*
- vii. *Oni, K. C. (2009). Adoption of Appropriate Agricultural Technologies for Commercial Arable Crops Farming in Nigeria. Paper presented at the Workshop on Commercial farming of Arable Crops in Nigeria at Kwara Hotels, Ilorin. 16th – 18th June, 2009.*